

GINNNGER

From Barriers to Action

Policy Insights for Advancing Urban
Regeneration in **Spain**

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About GINNGER

The GINNGER project aims to create new, inclusive and participatory processes for **neighbourhood regeneration**. A **methodology** to support collaborative **decision-making** is at the project's core. GINNGER is also designing and implementing regeneration plans across six pilot sites in Europe. Four key areas of regeneration are involved: energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources and sustainable mobility.

**GINNGER | Co-designing
neighbourhood regeneration**

The Spanish policy context

Spain has a broad regulatory framework supporting urban regeneration and the energy transition. However, implementation often depends on coordination across governance levels and local administrative capacity. In addition, translating EU objectives into practice often faces **fragmented competencies** and limited integration of **participatory processes** in planning.

Spanish legislation on this topic includes:

- Law 8/2013 on Urban Rehabilitation, Regeneration and Renovation.¹
- Royal Decree 244/2019, of April 5, regulation for self-consumption of electrical energy.²
- Royal Decree 390/2021 – Energy Performance Certification.³
- Law 7/2021 on Climate Change and Energy Transition⁴ and the Just Transition Strategy (2020).⁵
- Law 9/2025, Sustainable mobility.⁶
- Spanish Circular Economy Strategy 2030⁷ on waste-management.
- Asturias Regional Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3 Asturias)⁸ and Asturias Digital Innovation Hub (ASDIH).⁹
- Regional strategies on energy transition and circular construction (Asturias and Murcia).¹⁰

Barriers, Opportunities and Recommendations

	Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear responsibilities between national, regional and municipal levels. • Fragmentation and complexity of procedures for implementing regeneration initiatives. • Limited financial instruments for small municipalities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative burden for integrated projects. • Complex alignment of EU and regional funding cycles. • Difficulties in coordinating heritage protection with energy-efficiency regulations.
	Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong policy alignment with the EU Green Deal, Renovation Wave, Mission Cities and Just Transition objectives. • Many regional initiatives promote local energy transition and sustainable mobility. • Community-Led Local Action Group (LAG Alto Nalón) fostering bottom-up projects in Langreo. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional support via S3 Asturias and Asturias Digital Innovation Hub (ASDIH). • Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP) for the municipality of Murcia, integrating active mobility, public transport, and public space management.
	Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the role of local authorities, and strengthen links between the Technical Building Code, collective self-consumption and local energy sharing schemes. • Simplify and harmonise procedures across municipalities to move towards a fully operational framework for energy communities. • Reinforce technical and financial support at the local level. • Simplify demand-response schemes with standardised baselines and clear remuneration to improve participation. • Integrate Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans and low emission zones. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up accompanying measures to address social equity, public transport and active mobility, in line with the regional mobility strategy. • Enhance secure access to high-resolution consumption data and define interoperability requirements between aggregators and energy management systems. • Recognise municipalities as facilitators of local energy communities and institutionalise co-creation processes.

Conclusions and next steps

The recommendations presented are **based on GINJGER's pilots of Murcia's and Langreo's experience**. In Langreo, the Just Transition context highlights the need for clearer frameworks enabling local energy communities and district-level solutions. In Murcia, the integration of mobility and renovation planning points to the value of harmonised municipal procedures. They aim to support authorities and policymakers to facilitating and standardising neighbourhood renovation and collaborative decision-making at the national and local level. During the next months, the project partners will expand this analysis, identifying **best practices and potential areas for harmonisation** in all pilot sites and in all four key areas of regeneration (energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources, and sustainable mobility).

Methodology

The analysis presented was based on data collected through the assessment of policy and regulatory drivers and barriers (conducted under GINJGER's Task 2.4), and through questionnaires circulated among pilot partners. It combined multi-level policy mapping with comparative inputs from the Spanish pilots and stakeholder consultation activities.

Sources and further information

¹ [BOE-A-2013-6938 Ley 8/2013, de 26 de junio, de rehabilitación, regeneración y renovación urbanas.](#)

² [BOE-A-2019-5089 Real Decreto 244/2019, de 5 de abril, por el que se regulan las condiciones administrativas, técnicas y económicas del autoconsumo de energía eléctrica.](#)

³ [BOE-A-2021-9176 Real Decreto 390/2021, de 1 de junio, por el que se aprueba el procedimiento básico para la certificación de la eficiencia energética de los edificios.](#)

⁴ [BOE-A-2021-8447 Ley 7/2021, de 20 de mayo, de cambio climático y transición energética.](#)

⁵ [Just Transition Strategy_ENG.pdf](#)

⁶ [BOE-A-2025-24545 Ley 9/2025, de 3 de diciembre, de Movilidad Sostenible.](#)

⁷ [Estrategia Española de Economía Circular y Planes de Acción](#)

⁸ [Estrategia de Especialización Inteligente - Ciencia Asturias](#)

⁹ [ASDIH - Qué es - IDEPA](#)

¹⁰ [Strategies integrating Just Transition in Asturias - Observatorio de Transición Justa de Asturias; EACS](#)

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